

A study on ion-solvent interactions of some sulfate compounds in aqueous tetrahydrofuran at different temperatures

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The densities and viscosities of ammonium sulfate, sodium sulfate, magnesium sulfate and aluminium sulfate in 40 mass% tetrahydrofuran + water mixture have been measured at temperatures 303, 308, 313 and 318 K. Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) and viscosity B -coefficients of these electrolytes are derived from these data supplemented with their densities and viscosities, respectively. The limiting apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ°) and experimental slopes (S_V^*) obtained from Masson equation have been interpreted in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions, respectively. The viscosity data have been analyzed using Jones-Dole equation. The V_ϕ° values vary with temperature as a power of series of temperature. The structure-making/breaking capacities of the electrolytes studied here have been inferred from the Hepler's criterion.

The volumetric behavior of solutes has been proved to be very useful in elucidating the various interactions occurring in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions¹. It has been found by a number of workers² that the addition of electrolyte could either break or make the structure of a liquid. Since viscosity is a property of the liquid which depends upon the intermolecular forces, the structural aspects of the liquid can be inferred from the viscosity of solutions at different concentrations and temperatures.

Tetrahydrofuran (THF), commercially known as cellosolves, is a good industrial solvent. It figures prominently in the high energy battery industry and has been found its application in the organic syntheses as manifested from physicochemical studies in this medium³. THF + H₂O mixtures are also important owing to the H-bonding between water and tetrahydrofuran.

In continuation of our earlier findings⁴⁻⁷, we present here the measurement of limiting apparent molar volume, experimental slope and viscosity B -coefficient for some metal and ammonium sulfates at different temperatures to obtain better insight into ion-solvent, ion-ion and solvent-solvent interactions.

Results and Discussion

The experimental values of densities (ρ_0) and viscosities (η_0) of pure THF and different mass% of THF + H₂O mixtures at 298, 303, 308, 313 and 318 K are recorded in Table 1. The results reveal that η_0 of the solvent mixtures (THF + H₂O) at all the temperatures increases rapidly to a maximum at about 40 mass% of THF and thereafter decreases. Such characteristics in the viscosity vs composi-

tion curve is a manifestation of strong specific interaction⁸ between unlike molecules predominated by H-bonding interaction.

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) were determined from the solvent-mixture and solution densities using the equation,

$$V_\phi = \frac{M}{\rho_0} - \frac{1000(\rho - \rho_0)}{c\rho_0} \quad (1)$$

where M is the molecular weight of the solute, c the molarity of the solution and the other symbols have their usual significance. The correction to V_ϕ due to hydrolysis of the electrolytes may be negligible, since the strong H-bonding⁸ between THF and H₂O will reduce the hydrolysis of these electrolytes by free water molecules considerably.

Application of Redlich-Meyer equation⁹ was not possible due to the lack of data on the compressibility and pressure variation of dielectric constant, necessary to calculate the theoretical slope S_V^* . Thus, the limiting apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ°) and experimental slopes (S_V^*) were obtained by computerized least-square methods using Masson equation¹⁰. Within the experimental error, our values for V_ϕ varied linearly with $c^{1/2}$ to follow the following equation.

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^\circ + S_V^* c^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where S_V^* is a constant dependent on charge and salt type and can be related to ion-ion interactions and V_ϕ° is related to ion-solvent interactions. The values of V_ϕ° and S_V^* together with standard errors are listed in Table 2. The negative values of S_V^* for all temperatures indicate the presence of weak ion-ion interactions in case of ammonium sulfate,

Table 1. Physical properties of pure tetrahydrofuran (THF) and different mass% of THF + H₂O mixtures at different temperatures

T(K)	ρ_o (g cm ⁻³)		η_o (cp)	
	This work	lit.	This work	lit.
(i) 20% THF :				
298	0.98668	0.98668 ^a	1.49002	1.49002 ^c
303	0.98488	-	1.31155	-
308	0.98309	0.98309 ^a	1.13310	1.13310 ^c
313	0.98019	-	1.05991	-
318	0.97730	0.97730 ^a	0.89670	0.89670 ^c
(ii) 40% THF :				
298	0.96640	0.96640 ^a	1.73210	1.73210 ^c
303	0.96381	-	1.52760	-
308	0.96120	0.96120 ^a	1.32310	1.32310 ^c
313	0.95359	-	1.18412	-
318	0.94598	0.94598 ^a	1.04516	1.04516 ^c
(iii) 60% THF :				
298	0.94600	0.94601 ^a	1.49040	1.49042 ^c
303	0.94204	-	1.33984	-
308	0.93810	0.93810 ^a	1.18930	1.18931 ^c
313	0.93338	-	1.07421	-
318	0.92864	0.92863 ^a	0.95910	0.95909 ^c
(iv) 80% THF :				
298	0.91592	-	0.91591 ^a	0.92371 ^c
303	0.91181	-	0.85386	-
308	0.90768	0.90768 ^a	0.78401	0.78400 ^c
313	0.90251	-	0.72270	-
318	0.89732	0.89732 ^a	0.66141	0.66140 ^c
(v) 100% (pure) THF :				
298	0.88072	0.88072 ^a 0.8870 ^b	0.46300	0.46300 ^c 0.46000 ^b
303	0.87595	-	0.44536	-
308	0.87116	0.87116 ^a	0.42770	0.42770 ^b
313	0.86627	-	0.40893	-
318	0.86140	0.86140 ^a	0.3917	0.39017 ^c

^aRefs. 4-7. ^b Refs. 6,7. ^c Ref. 18.

sodium sulfate and aluminium sulfate. As expected S_V^* value decreases with rise in temperature in solvent-mixture for ammonium and aluminium sulfates which is attributed to more violent thermal agitation at higher temperature resulting in diminishing the force of ion-ion interactions (ionic dissociation)¹¹. The positive and large value of S_V^* for all studied temperatures indicates the presence of strong ion-ion interaction for magnesium sulfate. The increase of S_V^* with increase of temperature in this solvent-mixture in case of sodium and magnesium sulfates suggests that more and more solute is accommodated in the void space left in the packing of large associated solvent molecules.

To examine the ion-solvent interactions, the values of V_ϕ^o can be used. Table 2 reveals that V_ϕ^o values increase with increasing temperature in case of ammonium and aluminium sulfates and decreases with increasing temperature in case of magnesium and sodium sulfates. This indicates that the solvent molecules are loosely attached to solute which expand with increase of temperature, thus resulting in higher values of V_ϕ^o at higher temperature for ammonium and aluminium sulfates, but for magnesium and sodium sulfates, more electrostrictive solvation occurs at higher temperature. Similar results were reported for some electrolytes in DMF + H₂O mixture¹².

The variation of ϕ_V^o with temperature of the electrolytes in this solvent-mixture follows the polynomial equation,

$$\phi_V^o = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 T + \alpha_3 T^2 \quad (3)$$

over the temperature range under the investigation. The coefficients α_i 's are evaluated and the following equations are obtained :

$$\phi_V^o = -516083.699 + 3250.867 T - 5.1055 T^2 \quad (4)$$

for ammonium sulfate

$$\phi_V^o = 494125.408 - 3171.497 T + 5.0933 T^2 \quad (5)$$

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ^o) and experimental slopes (S_V^*) together with standard errors of different salts in 40 mass% THF + water at different temperatures^a

Salts	(V_ϕ^o) (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)				S_V^* (cm ³ dm ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2})			
	303	308	313	318 K	303	308	313	318 K
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	198.243 (±1.50)	855.277 (±1.90)	1257.036 (±1.22)	2199.71 (±1.60)	-461.341 (±0.96)	-1958.480 (±3.11)	-2954.390 (±4.61)	-5189.390 (±2.66)
Na ₂ SO ₄	772.446 (±1.67)	474.990 (±2.50)	432.109 (±3.41)	395.997 (±4.10)	-1969.370 (±2.23)	-1111.680 (±3.39)	-807.784 (±2.59)	-932.239 (±1.63)
MgSO ₄	-741.426 (±5.01)	-1056.890 (±0.90)	-1263.030 (±2.56)	-1506.240 (±6.11)	1838.357 (±4.48)	2656.686 (±3.39)	3262.604 (±2.01)	3883.211 (±1.11)
Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	931.711 (±1.91)	6239.947 (±2.39)	6461.712 (±1.42)	8893.751 (±3.61)	-2978.210 (±2.09)	-22276.500 (±1.18)	-23213.500 (±2.08)	-32754.800 (±2.05)

^aValues in parenthesis are standard errors.

for sodium sulfate

$$\phi_V^{\circ} = 222426.752 - 1399.032 T + 2.1865 T^2 \quad (6)$$

for magnesium sulfate

$$\phi_V^{\circ} = -9814543.783 + 63218.323 T - 101.729 T^2 \quad (7)$$

for aluminium sulfate

The limiting apparent molar expansibilities, $\phi_E^{\circ} = (\delta\phi_V^{\circ}/\delta T)_P$ calculated from equations (4–7) for all the electrolytes are included in Table 3. It is evident that ϕ_E° decreases with increase in temperature for ammonium and aluminium sulfates and is in accordance with the findings of Millero^{1,13}. Table 3 also shows that ϕ_E° increases with rise in temperature for sodium and magnesium sulfates. The increase and decrease in ϕ_E° with the increase in temperature can be ascribed to the presence and absence of caging effect^{2d}, respectively.

Table 3. Limiting apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E°) for various electrolytes in 40 mass% THF + water at different temperatures

Electrolyte	ϕ_E° (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)			
	303	308	313	318 K
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	156.934	105.879	54.824	3.769
Na ₂ SO ₄	-84.957	-34.025	16.908	67.841
MgSO ₄	-74.025	-52.160	-30.205	-8.431
Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	1570.549	553.259	-464.031	-1481.321

It is also observed from equations (4–7) that $(\partial^2 V_{\phi}^{\circ}/\delta T^2)$ for solutions of ammonium and aluminium sulfates is negative whereas it is positive for sodium and magnesium sulfates showing thereby that ammonium and aluminium sulfates behave as structure-breaker while sodium and magnesium sulfates behaves as structure-maker in this mixed solvent system keeping in view of the work of Hepler¹⁴.

The relative viscosities of solutions for various electrolytes (ammonium, sodium, magnesium and aluminium sulfates) in 40 mass% THF + H₂O mixture at different temperatures were determined and analyzed by Jones-Dole¹⁵ equation,

$$(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/c^{1/2} = A + B c^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

where $\eta = (Kt - L/t)P$

η_0 and η are the viscosities of solvent-mixture and solution, respectively, A and B are constants, ρ is the density of the particular solvent-mixture or solution and K and L are constants for a particular viscometer. The values of A and B were calculated by computerized least-squares method and are recorded in Table 4. The results reveal that the values of B -coefficient decrease with rise in temperature for sodium and magnesium sulfates whereas increase with rise in temperature for ammonium and aluminium sulfates in this solvent-mixture. This indicates that electrostrictive solvation is more at higher temperature for sodium and magnesium sulfates and in case of ammonium and aluminium sulfates the solvent molecules are loosely attached to solute which expand with rise in temperature. Similar results were reported for some metal sulfates in DMF + H₂O mixtures¹⁶ at different temperatures.

It has been reported by a number of workers that dB/dT is a good and reasonable criterion¹⁷ for determining the structure-making/breaking nature of any electrolyte. It is also evident from Table 4 that the values of dB/dT are negative for sodium and magnesium sulfates and positive in case of ammonium and aluminium sulfates, suggesting structure-making tendency of sodium and magnesium sulfates and structure-breaking tendency of ammonium and aluminium sulfates in this mixed solvent system. These conclusions are in excellent agreement with that drawn from $(\partial^2 V_{\phi}^{\circ}/\delta T^2)_P$ explained earlier.

Table 4. Values of B (cm³ mol⁻¹) and A (cm^{3/2} mol^{-1/2}) parameters together with standard errors for different electrolytes in 40 mass% THF + H₂O mixture at different temperatures*

Electrolyte	B values				A values			
	303	308	313	318 K	303	308	313	318 K
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	5.294 (±1.28)	5.676 (±1.01)	6.114 (±1.17)	7.497 (±2.01)	-2.621 (±1.77)	-2.690 (±2.78)	-2.808 (±1.36)	-3.343 (±1.56)
Na ₂ SO ₄	6.350 (±2.21)	5.378 (±2.81)	5.291 (±1.19)	5.211 (±2.18)	-2.836 (±3.02)	-2.519 (±2.81)	-2.486 (±1.35)	-2.412 (±1.55)
MgSO ₄	7.175 (±3.01)	6.333 (±2.19)	6.123 (±1.79)	6.003 (±1.88)	-3.376 (±1.14)	-3.037 (±0.99)	-2.968 (±2.22)	-2.955 (±1.91)
Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	15.326 (±1.83)	16.510 (±0.91)	17.408 (±1.11)	17.945 (±1.99)	-4.984 (±2.08)	-5.391 (±3.21)	-5.615 (±0.70)	-5.765 (±1.89)

*Values in parenthesis are standard errors.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran (Merck) was kept several days over KOH, refluxed for 24 h and distilled over LiAlH_4 . The boiling point (66°), density (0.8807 g cm^{-3}) and viscosity (0.0046 p) compared well with the literature values¹⁸. The specific conductance of tetrahydrofuran was *ca.* $0.81 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 25° .

Ammonium sulfate, sodium sulfate, magnesium sulfate and aluminium sulfate (SD fine chemicals, A.R.) were used as such, after drying over P_2O_5 . A stock solution for each salt was prepared by mass, and the working solutions were obtained by mass dilution. The conversion of molality to molarity was done using density values.

The density was measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer having a bulb volume of 25 cm^3 and an internal diameter of the capillary of $\sim 0.1 \text{ cm}$. It was calibrated at 298, 308 and 318 K with double-distilled water and benzene. The pycnometer with the test solution was equilibrated in a water-bath maintained at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$) by means of a mercury-in-glass thermoregulator, and the absolute temperature was determined by a calibrated platinum resistance thermometer and Muller bridge. The pycnometer was then removed from the thermostatic bath, properly dried, and weighed. The evaporation losses remained insignificant during the time of actual measurements. An average of triplicate measurements was taken into account. The density values were reproducible to $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. Details have been described earlier⁷. The viscosity was measured by means of a suspended-level Ubbelohde¹⁹ viscometer at the desired temperature (accuracy $\pm 0.01^\circ$). The precision of the viscosity measurement was 0.05%. Details have been described earlier⁴.

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